

cDNA for Long-Read Sequencing- COSMOS 2023

 Forked from [cDNA for Long-Read Sequencing](#)

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ABSTRACT

This beginner-friendly protocol is to make cDNA for long-read sequencing libraries from C2C12 differentiation time course, where each group gets one timepoint and replicate.

MATERIALS

EQUIPMENT/ SUPPLIES

- Qubit Fluorometer
- BA Analyzer
- Thermal Cyclers
- Thermomixer
- Magnetic Rack
- Qubit Assay Tubes
- 0.5 mL Tubes
- 1.5 mL Tubes
- PCR Tubes

REAGENTS

Light sensitive dyes (keep in dark):

- **Qubit RNA HS Assay Kit** (dye to measure RNA)
- **Qubit dsDNA HS Assay Kit** (dye to measure DNA)

Keep on ice:

- **RNase Inhibitor** (prevents RNA from being degraded)
- **Maxima H(-)** (reverse transcriptase enzyme)
- **5X RT buffer** (buffer for reverse transcriptase)
- **SeqAmp DNA polymerase** (DNA polymerase for amplification)
- **SeqAmp PCR Buffer** (buffer for DNA polymerase)
- **Oligo-dT primer (10 μM)** (primer for priming reaction)
- **TSO primer (10 μM)** (primer for 1st strand reaction)
- **IS PCR primer (10 μM)** (primer for PCR)
- **dNTPs (10 mM)** (deoxynucleoside triphosphates mix)

Keep at room temp:

- **Ampure XP beads** (for clean-up reactions)
- **Nuclease-free H₂O**
- **Elution buffer** (buffer for final cDNA)

Protocol Info: Jasmine Sakr:
cDNA for Long-Read
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protocols.io
<https://protocols.io/view/cdna-for-long-read-sequencing-cosmos-2023-cxbsxine>

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Measure RNA concentration

1 Calculate 400 ng RNA input to make cDNA.

1.1 Need the sample concentration from the Qubit to determine how many # μL of RNA we need to get 400 ng total.

$$400ng * \left[\frac{1\mu L}{RNAng} \right] = RNA\mu L$$

concentration
(inverse)
Volume of
RNA from sample

cDNA Experiment Overview

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Edited from Picelli, et.al (2014)

Prepare Reagents

3 Prepare the following reagent in 0.5 mL tube :

Dilute RNase Inhibitor

- 1 μL RNase Inhibitor
- 9.5 μL Nuclease-free H₂O

Mix with a P20 set at 6 μL

Make Master Mixes

4 Make the following two master mixes :

4.1 1. Label PCR tube with group #
2. In the labeled PCR tube, make the following **Priming Master Mix** :

- 2 μL *dilute* RNase Inhibitor
- 1 μL dNTPs [M] 10 millimolar (mM)
- 1 μL Nuclease-free H₂O

4.2 1. Label a 1.5 mL tube "FSMM"
2. In the labeled 1.5 mL tube, make the following **1st Strand Master Mix** :

(1 sample + 0.5 extra)

- 6 μL 5x RT buffer
- 3 μL TSO oligo [M] 10 micromolar (μM)
- 9 μL Nuclease-free H₂O

Priming & 1st Strand Reaction

5 **Priming Reaction**

Annealing of oligo-dT oligonucleotides on poly(A)-tail of mRNA is responsible for the priming of the RT reaction.

5.1 Add the RNA + Nuclease-free H₂O to the labeled PCR tube and mix by pipetting.

5.2 Start the **PRIM_FS** program on the Thermal Cycler.

- 00:03:00

5.3 During the 50 °C "HOLD":

1. **KEEP** tubes in Thermal Cycler and add 1 µL of Oligo-dT
2. **KEEP** tubes in Thermal Cycler and mix with P20 pipet set at 3 µL
3. Press "Skip Step" on the Thermal Cycler to proceed to the next step

- 00:03:00

Safety information

PROCEED TO NEXT STEP *IN THIS PROTOCOL*, **DO NOT WAIT** AFTER 3 MINUTES TO PROCEED

6 1st Strand Reaction

Reverse Transcription of first strand and addition TSO oligo to enable template switching.

6.1

WHILE the samples are priming in the previous step:

1. Prep the 1st Strand Master Mix by putting it on the Thermomixer at 00:01:00
2. Add 1.5 µL Maxima H (-) to the 1st Strand Master Mix
3. Mix with P20 set at 50 °C

6.2 After RNA has been primed at 00:03:00 (STEP 5.3):

1h 35m

1. **KEEP** tubes in Thermal Cycler and add 13 µL 1st Strand Master Mix + **Maxima H (-)** master mix
2. **KEEP** tubes in Thermal Cycler and mix with P20 set at 13 µL

Close tubes and the lid of the Thermal Cycler and let the program continue.

The program will run the following steps:

- Extend at $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 01:30:00
- Denature at $85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 00:05:00
- HOLD at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

PCR Amplification

7 Amplify cDNA with Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

Amplification using a single primer, *ISPCR primer*.

- 7.1
1. Take the PCR tube out from the Thermo Cycler to a rack On ice
 2. Label a 1.5 mL tube PMM and make the following **PCR Master Mix** On ice :

(1 sample + 0.5 extra)

- $37.4\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ SeqAmp PCR buffer
- $1.5\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ IS Primer $10\text{ }\mu\text{M}$
- $4.5\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ Nuclease-free H_2O
- $1.5\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ SeqAmp Polymerase

- 7.2
- Add $30\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ PCR Master Mix to the PCR tube
 - Mix with a P200 set at $30\text{ }\mu\text{L}$
 - MOVE IT TO THE *NEW* THERMAL CYCLER (ASK WHICH ONE)

- 7.3 Start the **AMP** program on the Thermal Cycler.

2h 53m

The program will run the following steps:

1. $95\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 00:01:00
2. $98\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 00:00:15
3. $65\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 00:00:30
4. $65\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 00:13:00
5. Return to **step 2** another **x10**

6. 72 °C for 00:10:00

7. 4 °C HOLD

Ampure XP Bead Clean-up

8 Clean up PCR reaction on Ampure XP Beads

Safety information

BEADS

Beads are heavy particles that settle that second you stop mixing them! Vortex *BEFORE* adding to *EACH* sample. Failure to do so will lead to variable bead concentration and affect the yield.

WASH STEPS

Make sure you go through the wash steps *QUICKLY!* We don't want the beads to dry out with our sample bound to them when they are exposed to air between the was steps! Dried beads will lead to lower yield.

- 8.1
1. Label new 1.5mL tube with group # and "cDNA" for the last step
 2. Add 90 μL Ampure XP Beads to tube and mix with the same pipet
 3. Incubate at Room temperature for 00:05:00
 4. Place tubes on a magnetic rack for 00:05:00
 5. **KEEP** tubes on the rack and remove solution using a pipet without touching the bead pellet
 6. **KEEP** tubes on the rack and add 200 μL of fresh 80% ethanol with P1000
 7. **KEEP** tubes on the rack and remove ethanol using a pipet without touching the bead pellet with P1000
 8. *Repeat:* **KEEP** tubes on the rack and add 200 μL of fresh 80% ethanol with P1000
 9. *Repeat:* **KEEP** tubes on the rack and remove ethanol using a pipet without touching the bead pellet with P1000
 10. Keep tubes open and air dry for no more than 00:02:00 Do NOT exceed time
 11. Take tubes off the magnetic rack and add 35 μL EB buffer
 12. Resuspend the bead pellet in the EB buffer by mixing with P200 set at 25 μL
 13. Incubate at Room temperature for 00:05:00
 14. Put samples back on the magnetic rack for 00:02:00
 15. Carefully recover 30 μL of sample and add to the labeled tube.

Qubit & BioAnalyzer

9 Measure concentration of cDNA using the Qubit.

9.1 The kit we use is very sensitive and detects a low range of DNA concentration, so we have to make a separate sample dilution to use when we measure concentration.

Make a 1:5 dilution (1 to 5 dilution), which means our dilute sample will be 5 times more dilute than the original sample.

Label a new 0.5 mL tube with group # and "dilute cDNA"

1 μL sample + 4 μL Nuclease-free H₂O = 5 μL diluted cDNA

Mix with P20 set at 3 μL

9.2

- Label a new Qubit Assay tube with group # and add the following:

1. Add 199 μL of Qubit 1x HS dDNA Buffer

2. Add 1 μL of *diluted* cDNA

- Vortex for 00:00:02
- Incubate Room temperature for 00:02:00
- Insert tube into the Qubit Fluorometer
- Click "1x DNA HS" and follow the on screen instructions

10 Check cDNA integrity and average bp length using the BioAnalyzer.

NOTES

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